

Development of Sustainable Lightweight Gypsum Composites with Enhanced Thermal Insulation Using Starch Gelatinization

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Abstract. The paper presents preliminary results of research on lightweight composite based on building gypsum. In order to improve the insulating properties of gypsum plasters, researchers often use various additives with thermal insulation properties, primarily aimed at enhancing the thermal performance of such gypsum composites. Examples include expanded cork granules or polystyrene granules. In this study, we decided to explore a different mechanism to increase the porosity of the composite without using such additives. For this purpose, we utilized the phenomenon of starch gelatinization directly in the fresh gypsum slurry. As a result, a material with very high porosity is obtained. The resulting composites exhibit porosity ranging from 60% to 90%, which significantly enhances their thermal insulation properties. We prepared a total of six types of mixtures, starting with a reference composition without starch, where the water-to-gypsum (W/G) ratio was 0.6. In each subsequent formulation, the amount of gypsum was reduced, allowing for the production of a final material with lower volume density. The fundamental properties of the gypsum composites obtained through this process were determined, including volume density in a dry state, thermal properties and compressive strength. The sorption properties of the materials were also examined using the dynamic water vapor sorption (DVS) method. This analysis provided sorption and desorption curves for composites of varying densities. Additionally, preliminary qualitative tests of the microstructure were conducted using a scanning electron microscope. The solution presented in this paper offers the advantage of producing a gypsum-based material with high porosity (>60%). Utilizing the starch gelatinization process directly within the slurry allows for the creation of a highly homogeneous material. In this process, the initial, temporary structure is formed by the starch gel, which serves as a framework around which the final gypsum-based structure develops after the gypsum's setting time is reached. The innovativeness of the tested material concerns a group of materials with very good thermal properties, with the use of an easily available, relatively cheap admixture in the form of starch. It can be used for the production of e.g. lightweight plasterboards, internal thermal insulation, blocks and partition wall panels. Due to its lightness and the possibility of incorporating natural-based additives such as starch, gypsum composites align with the concept of sustainable construction, reducing resource consumption and CO₂ emissions.

Keywords: lightweight gypsum composites; starch; thermal properties.

1 Introduction

In order to improve the properties of gypsum plasters, researchers often use various additives with thermal insulation properties, primarily aimed at enhancing the thermal performance of such gypsum composites. Examples include expanded cork granules [1], [2], [3], microspheres, aerogels [4], [5] or expanded polystyrene [6].

One approach to improving the thermal properties of gypsum composites is the addition of thermal insulation materials, as presented in the study [7], where EPS waste and mineral wool were utilized. The primary goal of this research was to develop lightweight materials with enhanced thermal insulation properties while contributing to sustainable construction practices through waste valorization. Overall, the study highlights an eco-friendly approach to construction material innovation, showing that waste-derived components can play a crucial role in improving both the environmental and functional performance of gypsum-based products.

From an environmental perspective, the use of waste materials is essential. Such tests were presented in the study [8], where the synergetic effects of coal fly ash and shot plant fibers on the thermophysical, mechanical and moisture-related properties of gypsum plaster were investigated. Combining 50 wt% coal fly ash with 6 wt% short plant fibers resulted in a lightweight gypsum composite with enhanced hygrothermal capabilities that met compressive strength requirements ($>2\text{MPa}$). The proposed gypsum composite showed a good application prospect in passive thermal and humidity regulation in buildings. Similar studies on the use of coal ash as an additive for lightweight gypsum blocks were presented in [9].

Another approach related to improve fire-resistance of gypsum composites by increasing the porosity is presented in [10]. The research shows the result of gypsum composites modified with coupling of naturally abundant clay mineral - palygorskite (0–30 wt%) and cost-effective glass fibre (0.5 wt%). The new board shows a commendable post-fire strength of 0.15 MPa and fewer cracks than commercial products, which are caused by increased porosity and the bridging effect of glass fibre and sintered palygorskite particles.

The study [11] investigated the development of a new lightweight gypsum composite incorporating barley straws treated with hot water and bio-based phase change material (PCM) to enhance its thermo-mechanical properties. The results demonstrated that the combined treatment of barley straws effectively improved the composite's thermal performance by increasing heat storage capacity and reducing thermal conductivity.

The use of starch as an additive in mortars and concretes has already been tested by many researchers. These studies focus primarily on the effect of starch on the rheological properties of fresh mixes. The study [12] examined the short- and long-term properties of lime mortars modified with a viscosity-modifying agent made from potato starch. The use of potato starch led to an increase in porosity and pore size, to a faster carbonation and was not detrimental to mechanical strength of the tested lime mortars. Similar research was presented in [13], where the viscosity

enhancer (a starch derivative) was used in lime-based rendering mortars to enhance rheological properties. The findings underline the importance of selecting suitable admixtures to tailor lime-based rendering mortars for specific requirements, providing a pathway to improve both the functionality and longevity of lime-based materials in building and restoration projects.

In the paper [14] the effects of using white flour, zinc oxide, and zinc ash as admixtures in mortar and concrete were investigated. The study aims to evaluate how these materials influence the workability, mechanical properties, and durability of the mixtures. White flour was tested for its potential to improve the consistency and adhesion of the mortar. The results indicate that the addition of white flour improved the mix's workability, making it easier to handle and apply. Overall, the inclusion of these admixtures demonstrated positive effects on both short-term and long-term performance, making them viable options for improving mortar and concrete properties in specific applications.

The studies presented above show, on one hand, how various types of waste materials are used to improve the thermal properties of gypsum composites. On the other hand, the introduction discusses the known methods of using starch in mortars. The current state of the art does not contain information on the research of mineral composites in which starch is directly gelatinized in the fresh slurry.

The research on the properties of the innovative materials proposed in this paper could potentially enable the production of composites with highly porous structures by gelatinizing starch directly in the gypsum slurry, thereby creating a material with very good thermal properties.

As shown above, this method of producing the composite is innovative, and the composites made using this particular method have not been tested so far. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct detailed fundamental research on their properties. The purpose of this publication is to present the preliminary results of tests on lightweight gypsum structures with high porosity obtained by the direct gelation of starch in a slurry.

2 Materials and Methods

In order to improve the insulating properties of gypsum composites we utilized the phenomenon of starch gelatinization directly in the fresh gypsum slurry. As a result, a material with very high porosity is obtained. Pure building gypsum $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \text{H}_2\text{O}$ was used. The water to gypsum ratio for the reference material is 0.6 and the initial setting time starts at about 3 minutes.

For each following recipes except G Ref additional potato starch in the amount of 35 g for 1 kg of water was added. After mixing the ingredients, the slurry was heated to approximately 65°C, at which starch gelatinization occurs.

The effect of direct heating of the mixed slurry of gypsum and starch was a highly porous material. Gelled starch initially formed a temporary and non-permanent skeleton. Once the gypsum began to set, the process of crystallization of the employed binder began around the gel-like structure of starch. As a result, it was

possible to create a durable and very homogeneous porous structure based on the employed building gypsum. The Table 1 presents the compositions of the individual mixtures.

Table 1. The composition of the tested composites.

No	Name	Building gypsum [g]	Water [g]	Starch [g]
1	G Ref	1667	1000	0
2	G 900	900	1000	35
3	G 700	700	1000	35
4	G 500	500	1000	35
5	G 325	325	1000	35

After 24 hours of curing the specimens were demolded and conditioned at $23\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\text{RH}=50\pm 5\%$ laboratory dry-air conditions, after which they were dried to a constant mass at 40°C for further tests [15]. For each type of the materials in question three specimens of the dimension of $\sim 50 \times 100 \times 100$ mm and three prisms $40 \times 40 \times 160$ mm were prepared.

The volume density tests were performed on the cuboid specimens $\sim 50 \times 100 \times 100$ mm. Measurements were conducted on three samples of each type of composite after drying them to a constant mass at a temperature of 40°C .

To obtain the results of thermal conductivity λ and volumetric specific heat c_v , tests were performed using a transient method (Isomet 2104 device). For this purpose, cuboid specimens were used. For each specimen type, a minimum of three samples, each around 40-50 mm thick, were cut and placed in a dryer at a temperature of 40°C until a constant weight was reached. The tests were carried out directly on the surfaces after cutting the cubic samples. This ensured a uniform and smooth surface for the measurements. A surface probe was utilized for these measurements, which involved analyzing temperature fluctuations in the tested material through the flow of heat pulses. Each presented result was obtained as the average of a total of six measurements.

The flexural test for each gypsum composite was conducted on three prism-shaped specimens measuring $40 \times 40 \times 160$ mm, in accordance with EN 13279-2 [15]. The final result of the test was the average of three measurements performed under controlled laboratory conditions. During the test, the prepared prisms were fractured into two sections. The resulting halves were subsequently utilized in repeated tests to ascertain the compressive strength of the mortar. The flexural strength was evaluated after 7 days of curing + the time for drying at 40°C .

The compressive strength tests of the composites were assessed in accordance EN 13279-2 [15]. The arithmetic mean of all six tested specimens for each material was presented as the result value.

Another test related to the sorption properties was conducted in accordance with the EN ISO 12571 standard [16]. The automated methods used to determine sorption isotherms serve as alternatives to traditional techniques [17]. Specifically, devices such as the Dynamic Vapor Sorption (DVS) apparatus were employed to generate moisture [18]. The apparatus monitored the change in mass over time (dm/dt) to determine the duration required to reach equilibrium. Once dm/dt approached zero, the system automatically adjusted to the next humidity level. An air temperature of 20°C and a relative humidity range of 0–97% were established, with humidity levels incremented by 10%. Each time the software detected a mass change of less than 0.0005% per minute, the relative humidity was automatically modified by 10%. Prior to testing, the specimens were dried to a constant weight at 40°C, with an initial weight of approximately 100 μg . To ensure dry conditions at the commencement of the measurement, the test began with 12 hours of sorption drying at a 0% humidity level within a nitrogen atmosphere.

A Hitachi TM3000 scanning electron microscope (SEM) was utilized to evaluate the quality of the contact zone between the starch gel the gypsum crystal structure. Specimens, measuring approximately 200 mm^2 in area and up to 3 mm in thickness, were prepared for analysis. To enhance the electrical conductivity of the tested surfaces, the samples were coated with metal alloys in a vacuum chamber. Images were captured at magnifications of 2000 \times .

3 Results and Discussion

Figure 1 presents a comparison of the microstructure of the tested gypsum composites at $\times 2000$ magnification. Image (a) shows the structure of the composite without starch admixture – typical needle-like crystals are visible, indicating a gypsum microstructure. In turn image (b) depicts the composite with starch admixture – larger and more irregular structures, as well as additional pores, can be observed. Individual crystals are "bonded" by the starch gel, forming a spatial structure. This suggests that the addition of starch alters the microstructure, likely increasing porosity and thus affecting the material's thermal and mechanical properties.

Fig. 1. The comparison of the microstructure of the tested composites (a) without starch and (b) with starch admixture.

As suggested above the additional pores affected the volume density of the tested materials. Figure 2 presents the densities of the particular composites. As expected the less binder used the smaller the densities. In case the of the G 325 the obtained volume density was three times smaller than the reference one. The decrease in density is quite well described by a logarithmic function, for which a high coefficient of determination was obtained.

Fig. 2. The volume density of the tested materials after drying at 40°C.

Proportionally to the changes in density, the thermal properties of the material also change (Figure 3). A significant decrease is already visible in the case of the G 900 composite (by 54% compared to G Ref). The lowest thermal conductivity value was obtained in the lightest composite G 325, for which the lambda was five times lower than in the reference sample.

The reduction in density and the simultaneous increase in the material's porosity also resulted in the expected decrease in volumetric specific heat. In the G 700 composite, the specific heat is approximately half the value of the reference

material, whereas in G325, it is again five times lower than in REF. In the case of both properties, due to their strong dependence on volume density, the logarithmic functions describing the obtained results also exhibited a high R^2 .

Fig. 3. The thermal properties of the tested materials after drying at 40°C.

The reduction in binder content in the composite resulted in a sharp decrease in compressive strength (Figure 4). The gypsum binder, with a standard W/G ratio of 0.6, achieved a compressive strength of 14.14 MPa. The lowest strength was recorded for the lightest composite, G325, at 1.21 MPa. Meanwhile, in G500, with a density of 0.5 g/cm³, the average compressive strength was 2.56 MPa. This value is sufficient for many applications where the material is not intended to serve a load-bearing function.

Fig. 4. The compressive strength of the tested materials after drying at 40°C.

The increase in porosity also had a clear impact on the sorption properties of the materials, as shown in Figures 5 and 6. In the case of both water vapor sorption and desorption, three groups of materials can be distinguished: REF samples, which

exhibit relatively low water absorption directly from the air; samples 900, 700, and 500, whose results are intermediate and quite similar to each other; and sample 325, which shows a significantly higher sorption capacity, especially at high RH levels. Due to the open pore structure, all materials exhibit virtually zero water retention during desorption.

Fig. 5. Sorption (a) and desorption (b) isotherms of the tested materials.

Fig. 6. Maximum sorption moisture of the tested composites at air humidity of 97%.

4 Conclusions

This research presents observations and comparisons on the thermal, strength, and sorption properties of gypsum composites with increased porosity obtained using the process of direct gelatinization of starch in fresh slurry. The results can be summarized as follows:

- The application of the starch gelatinization process directly in the fresh slurry allows for obtaining an ultra-light gypsum composite with a density as low as 0.37 g/cm^3 .
- Such materials exhibit significantly lower thermal conductivity—up to five times lower than the reference material. For instance, G 325 has a thermal conductivity of $0.07 \text{ W/(m}\cdot\text{K)}$.
- However, the reduction in density significantly decreases compressive strength. In the extreme case, the compressive strength of G 235 was 1.21 MPa , which is only 8.5% of the G REF value.
- The increase in porosity also leads to an enhancement of sorption properties. Among the tested composites, the maximum sorption value at 97% relative humidity (RH) increased from 0.95% for G REF to 3.30% for G 235.

The innovativeness of the tested material concerns a group of composites with very good thermal properties, with the use of an easily available, relatively cheap admixture in the form of starch. It can be used for the production of e.g. lightweight plasterboards, internal thermal insulation, blocks and partition wall panels. Due to its lightness and the possibility of incorporating natural-based additives such as starch, gypsum composites align with the concept of sustainable construction, reducing resource consumption and CO_2 emissions.

Acknowledgments

This research was funded in part by National Science Centre, Poland 2023/51/D/ST8/00107. For the purpose of Open Access, the author has applied a CC-BY public copyright licence to any Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM) version arising from this submission.

This preprint has not undergone peer review (when applicable) or any post-submission improvements or corrections. The Version of Record of this contribution is published in *Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering* (Springer), and is available online at https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-032-14011-1_57.

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